

Climate2Energy

A framework to consistently including climate change in energy systems modeling

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Evolving emissions and unfolding climate change call for better climate-to-energy conversions

[UNEP, 2024]

Many possible futures

The challenge

Climate model output

Solution:
Climate2Energy

Energy model input

#1: We are past the point where it was enough to investigate wind energy in isolation

Good climate-to-energy conversions should

1. Cover all important **technologies** with sufficient **technological complexity**
2. Include **bias correction**
3. Account for climate **variability** and climate change
4. Use best possible **inputs**
5. Openly available and modifiable

[Wohland et al., 2023]

[Senger et al., 2024]

[Wohland et al., 2019]

While amazing datasets exist (PECDv4.1; Bloomfield et al., 2021), there is a need for a formalized approach to allow methodological progress!

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#2: Climate Change impact assessment for wind energy that do not quantify multidecadal climate variability are inadequate

We cover climate variability and climate change

11-member CESM2 ensemble without tailored outputs

Member	Historical 1995-2015	SSP-3.70 2080-2100
Randomly chosen	A	A
Most positive NAO	B	B
Most negative NAO	C	C

Rerun CESM2 with tailored hourly output

Analyze all combinations (AA, AB etc.)

Results

Uncertain future PV changes in Finland

Climate variability

Consistent hydropower inflow reductions in Spain

Climate variability

9 realizations: a closer look

What does AA etc. mean?

AB

Realization used in the future

Realization used in the bias correction

Why is it OK to use A with bias correction B?

No memory in the atmosphere on timescales of 100 years

→ All three versions of the 1995-2015 climate are consistent with each version of the 2080-2100 climate

Mean changes in generation and demand

SSP-3.7.0 2080-2100 minus 1995-2015

Big picture:

- PV increases modestly
- Wind decreases modestly
- Hydropower drops strongly in Southern Europe
- Cooling demand skyrockets
- Heating demand shrinks considerably

Seasonal changes strongest for hydro and demand

Mostly summer reductions

Melt peak disappears

Future summer cooling > current winter electrical heating

Cooling grows strongly but still small compared to heating

Air density correction: how we do it

Basic problem

- We do not have access to power curves specific to variable air density
- Idea: package air density change as wind speed change and use the standard power curve
 - following Svenningsen, 2010 who follow IEC 61400-12

Approach

$$WED(\rho_{std}, v') = WED(\rho, v)$$

(compute pseudo wind speed v' that yields the same WED when used with fixed standard air density, as we would obtain when using the correct air density and correct wind speed)

$$v' = \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_{std}}\right)^{1/3} v$$

Then use power curve with v'

Air density correction: does it matter?

20y mean capacity factor (SWT120-3600)

- Historical: overestimation in warmer climates (as expected)
- Historical – SSP370: clear and weak thermodynamically induces CF decline (≤ 0.01)

Seasonal cycle in France

- Deeper summer dip in future

Effect is systematic, plausible and small.

Depends on specific application whether variable air density important enough to be included

Take home

- Formalized approach to compute renewable generation and demand for heating and cooling
- Here used with CESM2 tailored climate model outputs
 - Modest reductions in PV and wind CFs
 - Strong reductions in heating demand
 - Very stark cooling demand increases
 - Changes in seasonal cycle
- Open source and we welcome suggestions, improvements, and collaborations

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Paper

Code

